

Effect of Ligands on Stoichiometry and Stereochemistry of Nickel(II) Complexes

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A correlation between stoichiometry and stereochemistry of the solid thiocyanate nickel(II) complexes with various quinoline derivatives as ligand has been studied. Six complexes have been prepared : hexacoordinated Ni(NCS)₂(Qu)₄, (Qu = quinoline); with monomeric pseudooctahedral configuration, pentacoordinated Ni(NCS)₂L₃ (L = 4-MeOQu, 6-MeOQu) with distorted trigonal bipyramidal or square-pyramid configuration; Ni(NCS)₂L₂ (L = Qu, 6-MeOQu) having polymeric pseudooctahedral or square-planar configuration (L = 2,4-MeO₂Qu). A comparison with the corresponding complexes of pyridine ligands has been made.

Heterocyclic amines and their derivatives, such as quinoline, piperidine and pyridine can be regarded as biogenetic amines. In addition, some of the derivatives are used as plastic additives which cause quenching of the reactions¹. Various nickel(II) complexes are also known as a good quenchers²

It is well known that coordination number and symmetry in mixed ligand complexes of the type NiX₂L_n (X = halide ions; L = derivative of heterocyclic amines; n = 2,4) depend to a great extent on the steric requirements of the ligand³. In these complexes there are various arrangements of donor atoms around nickel(II) ion⁴. When such complexes are formed, electronic and steric properties of the ligands and their mutual interactions play an important role⁵ in stabilising these arrangements. From this viewpoint our attention was drawn to the study of stoichiometry and stereochemistry of nickel(II) thiocyanate complexes with quinoline and its derivatives.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of nickel thiocyanate with quinoline and substituted quinoline was carried out in benzene to give a number of complexes as listed in Table 1. Relevant conclusions concerning their stereochemistry were drawn from stoichiometry, electronic spectra, infrared spectra, molar conductance, magnetic moment and molecular structure determination. The low molar conductance values of the complexes (14–22 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in dimethylsulphoxide (10⁻³ M solution) indi-

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd*	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)				
	C	H	N	S	Ni
Ni(NCS) ₂ (Qu) ₄	66.21 (66.08)	4.32 4.06	12.32 12.17	9.22 9.27	8.13 8.40
Ni(NCS) ₂ (4-MeOQu) ₃	58.76 (58.98)	4.24 4.14	10.63 10.75	9.88 9.83	8.67 8.92
Ni(NCS) ₂ (6-MeOQu) ₃	59.21 (58.98)	4.02 4.14	10.93 10.75	10.12 9.83	9.23 8.92
Ni(NCS) ₂ (Qu) ₂	55.84 (55.55)	3.31 3.24	13.14 12.96	14.62 14.81	13.64 13.43
Ni(NCS) ₂ (6-MeOQu) ₂	53.26 (53.66)	3.52 3.66	11.55 11.38	12.89 13.01	11.62 11.78
Ni(NCS) ₂ (2,4-MeO ₂ Qu) ₂	57.34 (57.14)	4.34 4.44	8.63 8.88	10.43 10.15	9.50 9.21

*Qu = quinoline, 4-MeOQu = 4-methoxyquinoline, 6-MeOQu = 6-methoxyquinoline, 2,4-MeO₂Qu = 2,4-dimethoxyquinoline

cate their non-electrolytic nature suggesting coordination of thiocyanate groups to nickel(II) ion. In the infrared spectra of all the complexes, appreciable perturbations are observed in the fundamental frequencies of the pyridine moiety. The bands at 1580–1590 (C—C) and 1545–1560 cm⁻¹ (C=N) of quinoline and substituted-quinoline shifted to higher frequencies in the spectra of their nickel thiocyanate complexes. Moreover, the pyridine ring vibrations of the uncoordinated ligands (980–995, 600–610 and 400–410 cm⁻¹) also underwent significant positive shifts in the spectra of

complexes. These features are consistent with coordination of quinoline and its derivatives via its pyridine ring nitrogen atom⁶

Partial structure determination was carried out for the complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{Qu})_4$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(6\text{-MeOQu})_3$ to get information about the bond lengths and arrangement of the ligands around the metal ion. Stoichiometry of the complexes arranges them into three groups: $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_4$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_3$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_2$.

Fig 1 Molecular structure of $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{Qu})_4$

Complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_4$ ($\text{L} = \text{Qu}$) The infrared absorption spectra indicate that NCS groups are terminally coordinated through the nitrogen atom only, since ν_{CN} band occurred at 2085 cm^{-1} and ν_{CS} band ($685\text{--}730\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was absent⁷. The effective magnetic moments ($2.89\text{--}3.11\text{ B.M.}$) and maxima of the absorption bands for these complexes are within the region usually found for paramagnetic pseudo-octahedral nickel(II) complexes⁸. Thus, the presence of three bands ($9200, 15600, 25800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the electronic spectra are due to the spin-allowed transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{1g}(P)$ in octahedral symmetry. However, the calculated energy difference between ${}^3E_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^3E_{1g}(F)$ levels (16600 cm^{-1}) is greater by about 6400 cm^{-1} than the difference $\nu_3 - \nu_2$ (10200 cm^{-1}). This difference indicates a considerable distortion for octahedral symmetry. This is presumably due to inter-ligand interaction and repulsion causing elongation of $\text{Ni}-\text{N}(\text{Qu})$ bonds and thus leading to distortion of the octahedral polyhedron. This assumption was confirmed by X-ray structure analysis. As shown in Fig 1, the structure of $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{Qu})_4$ is characterised by an octahedral metal atom core with the axial positions occupied by the two nitrogen atoms from thiocyanate groups ($\text{Ni}-\text{N}(\text{NCS}) = 1.980\text{ \AA}$) and the equatorial plane is formed by four nitrogen atoms from the quinoline molecules ($\text{Ni}-\text{N}_1 = 2.420$ and $\text{Ni}-\text{N}_2 = 2.480\text{ \AA}$). The structural data of $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{Qu})_4$ complex indicates considerable increase of $\text{Ni}-\text{N}(\text{Qu})$ interatomic distances compared with those for analogous pyridine complexes⁹.

Complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_3$ ($\text{L} = 4$ or 6-MeOQu)

The stoichiometry of these complexes indicate monomeric pentacoordinated or polymeric hexacoordinated nickel(II) complexes. Both the complexes show a strong CN and CS stretching bands at $2075\text{--}2085$ and $810\text{--}815\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, suggesting terminally bonded

thiocyanate groups through the nitrogen atom. A further indication for the pentacoordinated Ni^{II} atom was obtained from the number and position of bands in the electronic absorption spectra¹⁰. Two idealised geometries for five-coordinated complexes, square-pyramid (C_{4v} symmetry) and trigonal bipyramid (D_{3h} symmetry) must be considered. Stereochemical considerations favoured D_{3h} symmetry¹¹ for which NCS groups occupied the axial positions of the trigonal bipyramid in order to decrease the steric strain. While on the basis of ligand field stabilisation energies, C_{4v} symmetry is favoured. Neither of the above suggestion was found by the X-ray structure analysis for $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(6\text{-MeOQu})_3$. As shown in Fig 2, the structure may be viewed as either highly distorted trigonal bipyramid or highly distorted square-pyramid similar to that observed in some nickel(II) cyanide complexes¹².

Complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{Qu}$, 6-MeOQu , $2,4\text{-MeO}_2\text{Qu}$) The stoichiometry of these complexes suggests four-coordinated nickel(II) atom. Two of them $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{Qu})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(6\text{-MeOQu})_2$, obtained thermally from the hexa- and pentacoordinated com-

Fig 2 Molecular structure of $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(6\text{-MeOQu})_3$

plexes, have effective magnetic moments of 2.89 and 3.01 B.M., and the maximum absorption bands resemble those for hexacoordinated octahedral complexes.^{8,13} A bidentate action of NCS groups in these complexes was observed from the infrared absorption spectra. The strong bands at 2120–2130 cm⁻¹ indicate a polymeric structure containing bidentate thiocyanate groups,^{7,13} since the ν_{CN} band observed at higher frequencies by about 40 cm⁻¹ compared with the same band for the monomeric hexa- and pentacoordinated complexes. The splitting of the first (8250–12600 cm⁻¹) and second (16400–18100 cm⁻¹) bands in the electronic absorption spectra suggests a tetragonal distortion in these complexes having the predicted NiN₄S₂ chromophore analogous to the distortion observed in complexes with pyridine ligands.^{13,14}

The appearance of ν_{CN} band at 2105 cm⁻¹ and ν_{CS} band at 850 cm⁻¹ for Ni(NCS)₂(2,4-MeOQu)₂·C₆H₆ indicates monodentate NCS groups. The low value of magnetic moment (0.23 B.M.) is probably due to temperature-independent susceptibility. The electronic spectra show a characteristic band with a maximum at 20150 cm⁻¹. On the basis of these results the compound can be considered as monomeric square-planar species with a basic singlet state ¹A_{1g}. This conclusion is supported by the comparison with the X-ray structural analysis of similar piperidine complex.¹⁵ This species may be formed by the square planar Ni(NCS)₂(2,4-MeO₂Qu)₂ molecules and by the molecules of benzene held together by the weak van der Waals forces. From the above discussion and by comparison of the stoichiometry and stereochemistry of quinoline and pyridine nickel(II) thiocyanate complexes the following conclusions can be drawn. Only hexacoordinated compound was obtained with unsubstituted quinoline, while such complexes were observed for both pyridine and substituted pyridine.^{4,9} This may be due to the steric factors which become effective for the bulky quinoline ligands. A comparison of Ni–N bond lengths between quinoline and pyridine complexes in axial and equatorial positions indicates a little tetragonal distortion for pyridine complexes (difference in axial and equatorial distance is between 0.060 and 0.112 Å). On the other hand, due to the size of quinoline, large tetragonal distortion was observed (difference in axial and equatorial distance is about 0.470 Å). The concept of the equatorial-axial interaction of the ligands¹⁶ is observed here.

for the complex Ni(NCS)₂(Qu)₄. The increase of the Ni–N (quinoline) distance in the equatorial plane results in decrease of the axial Ni–N (thiocyanate) distance (in comparison with that of pyridine ligands).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Nickel thiocyanate was prepared according to standard procedure.⁷

Preparation of the complexes. Nickel thiocyanate complex of quinoline Ni(NCS)₂(Qu)₄ was prepared by adding quinoline (5.16 g, 0.04 mol) dissolved in a minimum amount of benzene to nickel thiocyanate (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) suspended in benzene (40 ml) in 1:4 metal-ligand ratio. The mixture was refluxed for 6–7 h, then allowed to cool and crystallize overnight. The chemical analysis of the greenish blue crystals showed this to be Ni(NCS)₂(Qu)₄. In a similar manner the complexes Ni(NCS)₂(4-MeOQu)₃, Ni(NCS)₂(6-MeOQu)₃, and Ni(NCS)₂(2,4-MeO₂Qu)₂·C₆H₆ were prepared. On heating these to 100–110 °C, complexes Ni(NCS)₂(Qu)₂ and Ni(NCS)₂(6-MeOQu)₂ were obtained.

The complexes were analysed for C, H, N, and S at Microanalytical Laboratories, West Germany. Nickel was determined gravimetrically as nickel dimethylglyoximate.¹⁷

Infrared spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature using CoHg(SCN)₄ as a reference. Molar conductance was determined on an electrolytic conductivity measuring apparatus (model MC-1) having a cell constant of 1.

Crystal data. The greenish blue crystals of Ni(NCS)₂(Qu)₄ crystallised at room temperature from benzene solution revealed monoclinic space group P2₁/c with unit-cell dimensions of a = 14.674 (3), b = 10.381 (5), c = 11.962 (2) Å, β = 107.38 (4)°. The dark green crystals of Ni(NCS)₂(6-MeOQu)₃ crystallised at room temperature from benzene solution revealed monoclinic space group P2₁/c with unit-cell dimensions of a = 11.212 (3), b = 14.823 (4), c = 9.542 (2) Å, β = 109.26 (6)°. In both the cases Cu–K_α radiation (λ = 1.542 Å) was used. Diffractometer data was refined by least-squares procedure to final R of 0.048 and 0.042.

respectively, with anisotropic thermal parameters and correction for anomalous dispersion and absorption. All the calculations were carried out using the computer programme SHELX¹⁸.

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